

ZnO and Fe₂TiO₅ nanoparticles obtained by green synthesis as active components of alginate food packaging films

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to develop an active alginate packaging film incorporating antioxidant Fe₂TiO₅ and antibacterial ZnO nanoparticles, obtained by green synthesis utilizing citrus peel waste. The average particle size was estimated as 10 nm for ZnO and 50 nm for Fe₂TiO₅. Films were prepared using 2.33% (w/v) sodium alginate with 0.11% (w/v) Fe₂TiO₅ and/or ZnO nanoparticles. The inclusion of nanoparticles resulted in a noticeable colour difference, reduced the transparency, increased UV light protection and improved thermal stability of the film. The dry matter content of the films was around 83%. Film solubility in distilled water was low (< 8%) mainly reflecting crosslinking of the alginate polymer and Ca²⁺-ions. The lowest swelling degree was obtained for the ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅–alginate film (178%). The efficiency of these packaging films was demonstrated through preservation of strawberry freshness. Alginate packaging film with a mixture of metal oxide nanoparticles can facilitate food safety and increase food shelf life.

1. Introduction

Development of advanced food packaging materials modified by nanotechnology, nanomaterials and nanoparticles has resulted in longer food shelf life and smart food packaging functions, tracing the path towards more sustainable packaging solutions (Ahmad et al., 2023). Food packaging material for the future needs actively to protect the food product, indicate and reduce spoilage, and extend product shelf life. The material should be composed of biodegradable and non-polluting components. Replacement of petrochemical plastic polluting food packaging films with biodegradable alternatives, such as polysaccharides - alginate, chitosan, starch, etc., lipids and proteins is an objective of upcoming packaging solutions. Biodegradable polymer films can be sourced from fruit and vegetable processing by-products, especially as about 45% of fruits and vegetables produced worldwide are presently wasted. Such a green approach would bring about recycling, increased worth, and reduce environmental pollution (Lau, Sabran, & Shafie, 2021; Sani et al., 2023). Sodium alginate, a derivative of alginate, is a non-toxic biodegradable polysaccharide, made up of guluronic and

manuronic acid molecules bound by 1 – 4 glycosidic bonds. The US-FDA generally regards this polysaccharide as safe (GRAS) (Teng, An, Chen, Zhang, & Zhao, 2021; Motelica et al., 2021). Sodium alginate is water soluble and can be easily functionalized. Cross-linking with polyvalent cations, such as Ca²⁺, makes sodium alginate water-resistant and applicable for food packaging films (Omerović et al., 2021; Giz et al., 2020; Omerović et al., 2021). Plasticizers, for instance glycerol, have been added to improve the mechanical properties of alginate packaging films, but both mechanical and barrier properties need to be further enhanced by incorporating nanoparticles, essential oils or plant extracts (Motelica et al., 2021).

The mechanical, thermal and barrier properties of biopolymer packaging films have been advanced by incorporation of metal oxide nanoparticles (Nikolic et al., 2021; Lopusiewicz et al., 2022). Alginate reinforced with metal oxide nanoparticles has been investigated in the form of hydrogels (Sattayapanich, Chaiwat, Boonmarte, Bureekaem, & Sutthasupa, 2022), films (Vizzi, Beltrame, Zanet, Vidic, & Manzano, 2020; Rizzotto et al., 2022; Motelica et al., 2021; Sarvanakumar et al., 2020) and coatings (Parreidt, Müller, & Schmid, 2018; Aziz & Salama,

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2021) for active food packaging. The antioxidant, antimicrobial and antifungal functions of biodegradable food packaging films, including alginate, have been improved by incorporation of metal oxide nanoparticles (Omerović et al., 2021).

Zinc-oxide (ZnO) is a semiconducting metal oxide extensively investigated for quite some time. Its broad application field includes food packaging and preservation (Zare et al., 2022). The US FDA considers ZnO nanoparticles (NPs) as GRAS. ZnO NPs displayed good antibacterial activity and have been used as components in food packaging composite materials (Phothisarattana, Wongphan, Promhwad, Promsoru, & Harnkarnujant, 2022; Shankar & Rhim, 2019; Motelica et al., 2021). However, the antibacterial activity of ZnO NPs is due to interactions with bacterial cells. Therefore, besides benefits, there are some risks of utilizing ZnO NPs in food packaging film as NPs may migrate and interact with human cells (Pei et al., 2022; Czyżowska & Barbasz, 2022). Titanium oxide NPs have also been investigated for use in food packaging (Nikolic, Vasiljevic, Auger, & Vidic, 2021; Omerovic et al., 2021; Saravanakumar et al., 2020). However, there are growing concerns over TiO₂ and its toxicity, especially food grade titanium dioxide (E171) (Han et al., 2021; Rodríguez-Ibarra et al., 2022; Fiordaliso et al., 2022). Recently, TiO₂ was barred from food products and animal feed in Europe (May 2021 and June 2021 – European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)). Recent research has focused on iron titanate (Fe₂TiO₅) nanoparticles as a biocompatible, antioxidant component of alginate films and a possible alternative to TiO₂ (Rizzotto et al., 2022). Compared to ZnO that showed cell damage at 0.5 mg/ml, even at 2 mg/ml Fe₂TiO₅ caused no damage to human Caco-2 epithelial cells.

Metal oxide nanoparticles can be produced by a variety of synthesis methods that influence the resulting NP structure, morphology and other properties (Nikolic et al., 2021; Bandeira et al., 2020). Green synthesis involves exploiting non-toxic and eco-friendly precursors in the process to reduce the need for toxic chemicals and high temperature, energy or pressure. This results in a more environmentally friendly method, lower production cost and less dangerous or hazardous waste (Verma, Pathak, Srivastava, Prawer, & Tomljenovic-Hanic, 2021; Jeevandanam et al., 2022). Different plant and microbial (yeast, algae, bacteria, fungi) extracts have been applied as precursors in the green synthesis process (Jeevandanam et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2018). Plant extracts contain phytochemicals that are safe, cheap and readily available reducing and capping agents for bottom-up green synthesis of metal oxide NPs. Water is most often used as the solvent. This type of synthesis process can be easily scaled up to industrial level. NPs obtained using green synthesis procedures have demonstrated increased biocompatibility and improved properties for a wide field of applications, including energy storage, waste water treatment, environmental protection and remediation and other bio-related applications (Yulianto et al., 2019; Verma et al., 2021; Salama & Abdel Aziz, 2023). Thus, for example ZnO NPs with varied morphology and properties have been produced using green synthesis involving different biological extracts, zinc precursors and modifications of the procedure including variations in reaction pH, time and temperature (Bandeira et al., 2020; Mallakpour, Sirous & Hussain, 2021). Uniform and non-agglomerated ZnO NPs were obtained using *Coriandrum sativum* extract by a simple process not requiring a calcination step (Salama & Abdel Aziz, 2023). Biodegradable waste such as fruit and vegetable peel is an affordable and renewable source of extracts used in green synthesis of metal oxides (Aswathi et al., 2022; Sani et al., 2023). Utilization of such waste products reduces environmental pollution. One such source is citrus peel from oranges and lemons that accounts for up to 50–60% of the total fruit weight (Aswathi et al., 2022). Application of dried and ground lemon peel powder in the synthesis process resulted in ZnO NPs with improved surface and optical properties (Abarna et al., 2019), while synthesis of ZnO NPs using orange fruit peel extract gave enhanced antibacterial activity (Thi et al., 2020).

In this work, a novel active packaging film was developed by incorporation into alginate of ZnO and Fe₂TiO₅ nanoparticles produced

by green synthesis using citrus peel extract. A preservation study of fresh strawberry fruit was performed. Previous research showed that Fe₂TiO₅ nanoparticles provide strong antioxidant activity and high safety with no measurable migration of metal ions from the alginate films to food simulants (Rizzotto et al., 2022). The aim of this study was to improve the functionality of this packaging using ZnO nanoparticles that show high antibacterial activity. The influence of both metal oxide nanoparticle components on fruit spoilage was examined. The study includes detailed structural and morphological characterization of the synthesized nanoparticles and analysis of antimicrobial properties against gram positive and gram negative pathogens: *Salmonella enteritidis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Enterococcus faecalis*. Synergy of the favourable antimicrobial properties of ZnO with the high antioxidant activity of Fe₂TiO₅ was aimed to achieve a prospective safe and active packaging solution.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Materials, reagents and solutions

The following precursors (all produced by Sigma Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany)) were used for synthesis of ZnO, Fe₂TiO₅ NPs and film preparation: iron(III) nonahydrate (Fe(NO₃)₃·9 H₂O, ACS reagent, purity ≥ 98%), zinc nitrate hexahydrate (Zn(NO₃)₂·6 H₂O, reagent grade, purity ≥ 98%), titanium isopropoxide (Ti(OCH)(CH₃)₂, purity 98%), oxalic acid (Puriss, purity ≥99%), sodium alginate, glycerol and calcium chloride dehydrate (puriss p.a. ACS reagent). Tryptic soy agar (TSA), tryptic soy broth (TSB) and 2,3,5-triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (TTC) were procured from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO, USA).

2.2. Green synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles

Mandarin orange (*Citrus reticulata*) peel was collected from mandarin oranges purchased at a local market. They were dried for 3–5 days under direct natural sunlight, and blended into fine powder. 1 g of powder was placed in a glass container with 50 ml of deionized water, kept stirring for 3 h and then transferred to a water bath where mixing continued at 60 °C for 1 h. Finally, the solution was passed through filter paper and the obtained aqueous mandarin orange extract was stored in a refrigerator. ZnO nanoparticles were produced using the green synthesis method described by Nava et al. (2017). Thus, 2 g of Zn(NO₃)₂·6 H₂O was mixed with 42.5 ml of mandarin extract and stirred for 1 h at 60 °C on a magnetic hotplate until evaporation and powder formation were complete. A detailed scheme of the particle preparation is shown in Fig. S1.

2.3. Green synthesis of Fe₂TiO₅ nanoparticles

Lemon (*Citrus limon*) peel was collected from spent lemons purchased at a local market. Pectin was extracted by boiling finely chopped up peel in water (1 kg peel, 3 l water) for 30 min. The solution was passed through filter paper and the pale-yellow aqueous lemon peel extract was stored in a refrigerator. This extract was used in green synthesis of Fe₂TiO₅. It replaced other chemicals commonly used in Fe₂TiO₅ synthesis as surfactants or capping agents (Ramezani, Davoodi, Malekizad, & Hosseinpour-Mashkani, 2015; Vasiljevic et al., 2020) and thus this method can be classified as green synthesis (Talebi et al., 2016). The precursors, 4 g Fe(NO₃)₃·9 H₂O and 1.4 g Ti(OCH)(CH₃)₂ were separately dissolved in 20 ml of ethanol. Lemon peel extract (30 ml) was added and the mixture stirred for 30 min on a magnetic hotplate. Afterwards, oxalic acid solution in ethanol was added by continuous stirring until a thick gel formed. The solution pH was around 2. The obtained gel was further heated to 150 °C in an oven where the gel dried and converted into powder form. The obtained powder was ground and then calcined at 750 °C for 3 h in a chamber furnace to obtain Fe₂TiO₅ nanoparticles. A detailed scheme of the particle preparation is shown in Fig. S2.

2.4. Characterization of ZnO and Fe₂TiO₅ nanoparticles

Study of the structure and morphology of ZnO and Fe₂TiO₅ NPs included recording X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns on a Rigaku Ultima IV diffractometer (Tokyo, Japan) range 10–90°, step 0.05 s, acquisition rate 1°/min, gathering Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra in the range 400–4000 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ on a Perkin Elmer Spectrum Two (Waltham, MA, USA), observing field emission electron microscopy (FESEM) images on a FEI Quanta FEG (Thermo Fischer Scientific, Waltham MA, USA), and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images on a FEI TECNAI F20 (Thermo Fischer Scientific, Waltham MA, USA) with an X-FEG emitter operated at 200 kV and taken with a Gatan Rio 16 CMOD camera, obtaining STEM images using a Gatan DigiSTEM II and a high angle annular dark field (HAADF) detector and collecting diffuse reflectance spectra (DRS) on a Shimadzu UV-2600 through an ISR Plus ISA (Kyoto, Japan), range 200–1400 nm. Absorbance spectra of the NPs were calculated as the Kubelka-Munk transformation of the measured DRS.

2.5. Synthesis and characterization of ZnO, Fe₂TiO₅ alginate films

Alginate film was prepared using the method previously described in (Vizzini et al., 2020; Rizzotto et al., 2022). Then ZnO, Fe₂TiO₅ and ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅ NPs were ultrasonically blended into the prepared gel. The obtained solutions were solution cast (4 ml) into Petri dishes (5 cm in diameter) and dried for 12 h at 50 °C. Film wetting (10 min) was done using 5% calcium chloride solution, followed by washing with distilled water, and subsequent drying at room temperature between two layers of thick filter paper (Whatman, Maidstone, UK). Some wrinkling was observed round the edges (as shown in Fig. S3) but it was not significant and measurements were possible.

Attenuated total reflection (ATR) Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy (range 400 - 4000 cm⁻¹, resolution 8 cm⁻¹) was applied to study film structure and composition with a Perkin Elmer Spectrum Two (Waltham, MA, USA), by directly measuring the films in at least three random places (Costa et al., 2018; Lopusiewicz et al., 2022). UV-Vis transmittance spectra, range 200–850 nm, step 1 nm, were recorded by placing the investigated films in a standard film sample holder using a Shimadzu UV-2600 spectrophotometer combined with an Integrating Sphere Attachment ISR-2600 Plus (Kyoto, Japan). The opacity value was calculated (Zhao, Wang & Liu, 2022): Opacity = A_{600}/x , with A_{600} denoting the absorbance at 600 nm and x denoting the film thickness in mm. Film transparency was determined as %Transmittance at 600 nm (Motelica et al., 2021). Film thickness was measured at several random positions on the films using a laboratory micrometer device and the average values were calculated (Lopusiewicz, Macieja, Sliwinski, Bartkowiak, & Roy, 2022).

The dry matter content, water solubility and swelling degree of the prepared films (specimen size 1 × 1 cm, measured in triplicate) were calculated as follows: dry matter content (%) = $m_2/m_1 \times 100$; solubility (%) = $(m_2 - m_4)/m_2 \times 100$; swelling degree (%) = $(m_3 - m_2)/m_2 \times 100$ using the gravimetric procedure described by Salevic et al. (2022) where m_1 is the initial film mass, m_2 is the dry film mass, m_3 is the film mass after immersion in distilled water for 24 h and m_4 is the final dry mass.

Colour analysis of the films was performed by direct measurement with a Chroma Meter CR-400 (Konica Minolta, Japan) and a white calibration plate ($Y = 84.8$, $x = 0.3199$ and $y = 0.3377$). Each sample was measured at five random positions on the film surface. The CIELAB scale (L^* , a^* , b^*) was used to determine the colour parameters (Choi, Lee, Iyu, Lee, & Han, 2022). The hue angle (h°) was determined as $\arctan(b^*/a^*)$, while chroma (C^*) was calculated as $(a^{*2} + b^{*2})^{1/2}$ (Belović et al., 2014). The total colour difference (ΔE^*) was calculated as:

$$\Delta E^* = \sqrt{(L_2^* - L_1^*)^2 + (a_2^* - a_1^*)^2 + (b_2^* - b_1^*)^2} \quad (1)$$

while the whiteness index (WI) was determined as:

$$WI = 100 - \sqrt{(100 - L^*)^2 + a^{*2} + b^{*2}} \quad (2)$$

TG/DTA analysis of film samples on a 6000 TG/DTA Perkin Elmer device (Waltham, MA, USA) was utilized to study thermal degradation behaviour (heating rate 10°/min in argon gas up to 500 °C).

2.6. Antimicrobial activity

Antibacterial activity of NPs was tested in triplicate on *Salmonella enteritidis* ATCC 22076, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) ATCC 25923, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, and *Enterococcus faecalis* ATCC 29212. Bacterial strains were sustained on TSA plates and retrieved by culturing in TSB. Minimum inhibitory (MIC) and minimum bactericidal (MBC) concentrations were established using the micro-dilution method as described previously (Klaus et al., 2015). In short: serial dilutions of NPs in TSB (0.156 mg/ml - 20 mg/ml) were prepared in flat-bottomed sterile 96-well microtiter plates (Sarstedt, Germany) and inoculated with TSB cultivated bacterial strains, incubated, followed by MIC and MBC determination with gentamicin as the positive control, bacterial dilutions in TSB as the negative control, and TSB alone as the sterility control.

2.7. Preservation study on fresh strawberry fruit

Strawberries were chosen as the target food for performing the preservation study. They are a fruit that perishes easily but is a popular and convenient healthy snack sold “ready to eat” both whole and cut (Paulsen, Barrios, & Lema, 2021; Avalos-Llano et al., 2018). Fresh strawberries were purchased from a local market store. They were washed with distilled water, dried in air at room temperature (25 °C) and then cut in half and covered with pieces of film (alginate, Fe₂TiO₅-alginate, ZnO-alginate and ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅-alginate). The study was conducted in open atmosphere at a temperature of around 18 °C and relative humidity of around 40%. Photographs were taken with a high resolution camera for 4 consecutive days to register evidence of physical deterioration, microbial and fungal infestation and growth. All experiments were done in triplicate.

2.8. Statistical analysis

Statistica software (version 6) was employed for statistical analysis of the obtained results. Analysis of variance (ANOVA), the post hoc Fisher test and Tukey honest significance difference (HSD) test at the significance threshold of $p < 0.05$ were applied to determine differences between means.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structure and morphology of ZnO nanoparticles

The green synthesized ZnO NPs were pale grey in colour (Fig. S1). ZnO powder is commonly white when the production route involves a calcination (annealing) stage at a high enough temperature applied for a long enough time (Thi et al., 2020). When the calcination temperature is lower and the time is shorter or this step is not applied, ZnO powder can have a different colour: black, grey, or even orange. The orange colour is caused by residues of the green synthesis process using orange peel extract (Thi et al., 2020). Our ZnO NPs were formed with no calcination step, hence their pale grey colour. The XRD pattern (Fig. 1a) revealed wide pure wurtzite P6₃mc phase ZnO crystalline lattice peaks (JCPDS card 36–1451). Wide peaks are indicative of nanoparticles and the TEM images (Figs. 1b and 1f) corroborate this (average NPs 10 nm). Selected area diffraction (SAED) analysis of a number of HRTEM images of the synthesized ZnO NPs validated XRD pattern analysis. An example is the

Fig. 1. XRD pattern (a), TEM image with phase analysis area marked as a red circle (b), SAED pattern of the red marked circle area and corresponding ZnO phase rings (c), FTIR (d), and UV-Vis absorbance with the red line and arrow showing the approximated excitation wavelength of 392 nm (e) spectra and higher magnification TEM image (f) of ZnO NPs.

area selected in the red circle in Fig. 1b and the corresponding SAED in Fig. 1c revealing diffraction ring patterns characteristic for NPs allocated to ZnO (JCPDS 36–1451). The structure of ZnO NPs was further evaluated by FTIR (Fig. 1d) revealing low intensity peaks ($\approx 3464 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) typical for H_2O vibrations on the NP surface (Thi et al., 2020). The other notable vibrations in the spectrum are due to traces of mandarin orange extract used in the green synthesis, namely aromatic $\text{C}=\text{C}$ bending at $\approx 1586 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Omran, Aboelazayem, Nassar El-Salamony, & El-Gendy, 2021), aromatic ring $\text{C}-\text{C}$ stretching at $\approx 1363 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Luque et al., 2018) and functional vibrations of $\text{Zn}-\text{OH}$ and $\text{C}-\text{H}$ aromatic bands at $\approx 846 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Thi et al., 2020; Luque et al., 2018). A broad band (200–400 nm, UV region) and approximated excitation wavelength of 392 nm was revealed in the determined ZnO absorbance spectrum (Fig. 1e) in correlation with previous findings (Motelica et al., 2021).

3.2. Structure and morphology of Fe_2TiO_5 nanoparticles

The green synthesized Fe_2TiO_5 NPs were light warm brown in colour due to the iron content in the powder (Fig. S2). Well-defined pure Fe_2TiO_5 phase crystalline peaks (orthorhombic Cmcm JCPDS card 76–1158) are revealed in the measured structure (XRD pattern) in Fig. 2a. Morphological investigation of Fe_2TiO_5 NPs (FESEM Fig. 2b, HRTEM Fig. 2c) revealed clusters of Fe_2TiO_5 NPs confirming previous morphological examinations of this material (Vasiljevic et al., 2020). Due to the calcination step in the synthesis procedure the average particle size for Fe_2TiO_5 (50 nm) was larger than for ZnO in line with previous research (Rizzotto et al., 2022). The study of HRTEM images further verified the presence of only Fe_2TiO_5 NPs in the synthesized powder. An example is given in Fig. 2c, where analysis of the marked part of the image using FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) provided the indicated lattice spacing of 0.35 nm that can be matched to the highest

intensity (110) peak (shown in the XRD in Fig. 2a). Further structural analysis by FTIR (Fig. 2d) revealed only vibrations ($\approx 800, 661, 618$ and 433 cm^{-1}) deriving from Fe and Ti–O group vibrations of Fe_2TiO_5 , in correlation with previous findings (Rizzotto et al., 2022). A marked wide light absorption spanning UV and visible portions of the spectrum up to 600 nm, with an excitation band at 571 nm, were noted for the absorbance spectrum (Fig. 2e) of the produced Fe_2TiO_5 NPs and can be correlated with similar spectra of Fe_2TiO_5 NPs and nanofibers (Vasiljevic et al., 2020; Vasiljevic et al., 2021). The absorption intensity was in line with values determined for Fe_2TiO_5 nanofibers fabricated at higher temperatures, such as 700 and 750 °C.

3.3. Antimicrobial activity of ZnO and Fe_2TiO_5 nanoparticles

ZnO NPs inhibited bacterial growth of all assessed strains but effectiveness was strain dependent (Table 1). Thus, antibacterial activity was similar against both Gram-negative species tested (*E. coli* and *S. enteritidis*), but quite different for the two Gram-positive bacteria. Indeed, the lowest ZnO NP MIC and MBC values were found against the MRSA strain, relatively resilient to gentamicin, while ZnO NPs had the least influence on the development of *E. faecalis*. In the case of Fe_2TiO_5 NPs, the MIC activity was above the tested maximal 20 mg/ml and MBC was not established for both Gram-positive and Gram-negative species, confirming previous findings that Fe_2TiO_5 shows no toxicity towards bacterial cells (Rizzotto et al., 2022).

Even though the ZnO NP mode of action on microorganisms has not been completely elucidated, ZnO NPs with diverse morphologies have been shown to kill many different microorganisms (Slavin, Asnis, Häfeli, & Bach, 2017; Azam et al., 2012; Gudkov et al., 2021; da Silva et al., 2019; Zanet et al., 2019). One crucial parameter seems to be NPs size, while the second is the type of targeted bacterial cell. The larger surface

Fig. 2. XRD pattern (a), FESEM image (b), HRTEM image with the blue rectangle marking the magnified part shown below that was analysed by Fast Fourier Transform with the red arrow depicting the lattice spacing of 0.35 nm that can be matched to the highest intensity X-ray diffraction peak (110) of Fe_2TiO_5 orthorhombic $Cmcm$ crystalline lattice (c), FTIR transmittance spectrum with main peaks marked with arrows (d) and UV-Vis absorbance spectrum absorbance with the red line and arrow showing the approximated excitation wavelength of 571 nm (e) of Fe_2TiO_5 NPs.

volume and multiple ions to interact with the medium or bacterial cells point to higher reactivity of smaller NPs. The estimated average size of ≈ 10 nm of the ZnO NPs synthesized in this work ensured a large surface volume and also internalization into bacterial cells combined with interactions with intracellular molecules (Stankic et al., 2016; Staroń & Długosz, 2021). High antibacterial effectiveness of ZnO NPs against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains tested suggests that they may exert multiple modes of action. In keeping with this, *E. faecalis* was affected the least and MBC was not established for the tested range of ZnO concentrations. The sensitivity of Gram-negative species to ZnO NPs may be due to the lipopolysaccharide and peptidoglycan thin layer design allowing easy introduction of toxic Zn^{2+} -ions and reactive

oxygen species (ROS) originating from ZnO NPs (Slavin et al., 2017; Zanet et al., 2019). Moreover, da Silva et al. (2019) showed that it may be due to the NP morphology. However, a Gram-positive species, *Bacillus subtilis* reacted notably to Mg-doped ZnO NPs (Auger et al., 2019) which triggered multiple mechanisms of bacteriostatic and bactericidal activity and involved perturbation in bacterial stress responses, biofilm formation, motility and chemotaxis, purine metabolism and translation.

3.4. Structure and properties of alginate-ZnO/ Fe_2TiO_5 films

As presented in Fig. 3 all produced films were transparent. The films containing ZnO and/or Fe_2TiO_5 NPs were yellow-grey to light brown.

Table 1

Antimicrobial activity of ZnO nanoparticles expressed as MIC and MBC determined by the broth microdilution method.

	ZnO		gentamicin	
	MIC (mg/ml)	MBC (mg/ml)	MIC (mg/ml)	MBC (mg/ml)
<i>S. enteritidis</i> ATCC 22076	1.25	20	0.024	0.024
<i>S. aureus</i> , MRSA, ATCC 25923	0.156	1.25	2.5	2.5
<i>E. coli</i> , ATCC 25922	1.25	10	0.0097	0.0097
<i>E. faecalis</i> , ATCC 29212	10	-	0.078	0.156

- not achieved. There are no standard deviations since there was no difference between repetitions.

The measured and calculated colour parameters are given in Table 2. Compared to the colour values measured for the white plate ($L^* = 93.23$, $a^* = -0.196$ and $b^* = 4.728$), the pure alginate film cross-linked with CaCl_2 showed a slight change, namely a decrease in the lightness value (L^*), an increase in the redness/greenness parameter (a^*) and decrease in the yellowness/blueness parameter (b^*). The colour parameters of the Fe_2TiO_5 -alginate films differed the most from the pure alginate film with the lowest L^* and highest a^* and b^* indicating noticeable colouring of the film with the highest total colour difference (ΔE^*) and lowest whiteness value (W). The ZnO-alginate films were the most similar to pure alginate films, with a slightly lower L^* and higher a^* and b^* . This difference was statistically significant as shown in Table 2, reflecting the yellow-grey colour shown in Fig. 3a. The ZnO/ Fe_2TiO_5 -alginate film had

colour parameter values in between the ZnO-alginate and Fe_2TiO_5 -alginate films, indicating the combined influence of the two different added nanoparticles. These films also showed the highest standard deviations indicating that the Zn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Ti^{4+} ions were distributed somewhat non-uniformly across the alginate film. Regarding the CIE parameters h° and C^* the hue was similar for all three films containing nanoparticles when compared to pure alginate film. Nevertheless, the difference was statistically significant, as shown in Table 2. The chroma C^* values also differed significantly, with the lowest obtained for pure alginate film and the highest for Fe_2TiO_5 -alginate film.

The UV-Vis transmittance spectrum measured for alginate film (Fig. 3b) had transmittance of 76.48% at 300 nm, increasing to 86.61% at 400 nm, 88.44% at 500 nm and reaching 89.4% at 800 nm., in line with previous alginate film research (Bai et al., 2020). For films containing NPs, the transmittance was generally lower. Composite NP-alginate films have previously shown lower transmittance which was connected with the NP content in the films and film thickness (Lopusiewicz et al., 2022; Motelica et al., 2021). UV light protection and light barriers are needed for quality food preservation in order to obstruct nutrient and vitamin decomposition and oxidation induced by light. ZnO has been employed before for this end (Motelica et al., 2021; Lopusiewicz et al., 2022). For Fe_2TiO_5 -alginate films transmittance was overall lower, changing from 38.54% at 300 nm, 41.81% at 400 nm, and 50.28% at 500 nm to 71.74% at 800 nm. These films offered some UV protection. The ZnO alginate films showed good UV protection, taking into account the optical properties of ZnO NPs displayed in Fig. 1e. The transmittance was 6.9% at 300 nm, increasing to 32.80% at 400 nm and 62.99% at 800 nm. In the case of ZnO/ Fe_2TiO_5 -alginate films, the change in transmittance echoed the presence of both types of NPs, with transmittance of 25.19% at 300 nm offering UV light barrier protection,

Fig. 3. Transparency (a), UV-Vis transmittance spectra (b), TG/DTA curves (c) and FTIR spectra (d) of alginate, Fe_2TiO_5 -alginate, ZnO-alginate and ZnO/ Fe_2TiO_5 -alginate films.

Table 2

Colour parameters (L^* , a^* , b^* , h° , C^* , WI and ΔE^*), transparency, opacity, dry matter content, solubility and swelling degree of alginate, Fe₂TiO₅-alginate, ZnO-alginate and ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅ – alginate films.

Parameters	Sample			
	Alginate	Fe ₂ TiO ₅ -alginate	ZnO-alginate	ZnO/Fe ₂ TiO ₅ -alginate
x (mm)	0.32 ± 0.04	0.31 ± 0.02	0.33 ± 0.02	0.33 ± 0.02
L^*	89.50 ± 0.63 ^a	79.16 ± 0.45 ^d	87.07 ± 1.69 ^b	80.95 ± 4.44 ^c
a^*	-0.43 ± 0.03 ^d	8.49 ± 0.27 ^a	0.63 ± 0.05 ^c	4.51 ± 0.84 ^b
b^*	8.26 ± 0.43 ^d	32.62 ± 0.83 ^a	11.81 ± 0.27 ^c	25.79 ± 2.71 ^b
h°	-1.518 ± 0.004 ^d	1.316 ± 0.003 ^c	1.517 ± 0.003 ^a	1.399 ± 0.015 ^b
C^*	8.27 ± 0.42 ^d	33.70 ± 0.87 ^a	11.83 ± 0.27 ^c	26.18 ± 2.81 ^b
WI	86.63 ± 0.66 ^a	60.37 ± 0.96 ^d	82.47 ± 0.31 ^b	67.61 ± 3.26 ^c
ΔE^*	5.15 ± 0.65 ^d	32.42 ± 0.97 ^a	9.42 ± 0.31 ^c	24.83 ± 3.29 ^b
Transparency (%)	89.01	65.26	56.76	62.01
Opacity (%)	0.16	0.59	0.74	0.63
Dry matter content (%)	83.13 ± 0.86 ^a	83.47 ± 0.81 ^a	82.72 ± 1.15 ^a	83.65 ± 0.51 ^a
Solubility (%)	4.26 ± 0.44 ^{a,b}	2.77 ± 0.31 ^b	7.49 ± 1.60 ^a	7.12 ± 2.09 ^a
Swelling degree (%)	263.08 ± 30.68 ^a	241.36 ± 72.91 ^a	308.08 ± 77.41 ^a	177.90 ± 32.14 ^a

Values are given as means ± standard deviation. Means with different letters (a, b, c and d) are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ (compared to other variants within the groups)

increasing to 42.08% at 400 nm and 69.32% at 800 nm, showing similar transparency in the visible domain to ZnO films. The measured transparency and calculated opacity values (at 600 nm) are shown in Table 2. Opacity varied between 0.16 for pure alginate film and 0.74 for ZnO-alginate films (Table 2). In all cases the films were fairly transparent, and the opacity was similar to other alginate films incorporating ZnO NPs (Motelica et al., 2021; Aziz & Salama, 2022).

Wetting the films with CaCl₂ ensured egg-box model type infiltration of calcium (Ca²⁺) ions into the films (Cao, Lu, Mata, Nishinari, & Fang, 2020; Wang, Wan, Wang, Li, & Zhu 2018). Alginate polymer chains in composite films are organized around the NPs. Addition of Ca²⁺ ions promoted further film strengthening (Motelica et al., 2021). The dry matter content in all film samples was comparable and relatively high, displaying dominant dependence on the CaCl₂ cross-linked alginate films rather than on the presence of ZnO and/or Fe₂TiO₅ NPs. As shown in Table 2 it varied between 82.72% and 83.65% creating moisture contents between 16.35% and 17.28%. Similar values were obtained before for alginate films (Alboofetileh et al., 2013).

The swelling degree varied depending on film composition (Table 2). All films swelled but preserved their integrity after 24 h agitated immersion in water. Pure and ZnO-alginate films displayed swelling values similar to those noted earlier (Wang et al., 2019). A similar swelling percentage was obtained by Motelica et al. (2021). Incorporation of Fe₂TiO₅ in the alginate matrix slightly reduced the degree of swelling, while the combination of ZnO and Fe₂TiO₅ NPs led to even lower values. Swelling degree has been linked with the extent of crosslinking (Choi et al., 2022; Costa et al., 2018). Thus, Costa et al. (2018) determined that adding a certain concentration of CaCl₂ increases the number of guluronic (G) blocks of alginate linked with calcium ions resulting in a high swelling degree. They explained this phenomenon with an “egg-box” model that enables film resistance to be high enough not to dissolve in water, but with strands still available for water uptake. Further increase of CaCl₂ concentrations led to more bonds and fewer strands available for swelling and thus a decrease in the swelling degree. Quadrado and

Fajardo (2017) showed that cross-linking alginate with Fe³⁺ ions resulted in a decrease in swelling degree. This was attributed to stronger reactions of Fe³⁺ ions with carboxyl and hydroxyl functional groups of alginate that lessened interaction of hydrophobic sites with water molecules leading to restricted network expansion. This phenomenon can explain the lower swelling degree noted for Fe₂TiO₅-alginate films, as they contain Fe³⁺ and Ti⁴⁺ ions as well as Ca²⁺ in the alginate matrix. Wang et al. (2019) showed that incorporation of ZnO and the presence of Zn²⁺ ions in the alginate matrix, besides Ca²⁺, resulted in an increased swelling degree, and this can explain the results obtained for ZnO-alginate films. In the case of the ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅ – alginate films, where the lowest swelling degree was obtained, the combined influence of metal ions originating from the two types of nanoparticles, i.e. Fe³⁺, Ti⁴⁺ and Zn²⁺ combined with Ca²⁺, led to an even larger level of reaction of metal ions with carboxyl and hydroxyl groups resulting in marked restriction in network expansion and a low swelling degree.

Film solubility in distilled water was low, and below 8% for all film samples. According to Roger, Talbot, and Bee (2006) low solubility of alginate films may be accomplished with a high concentration of Ca²⁺ ions. Elevated crosslinking levels obstruct alginate dissolution, and lessen swelling and film solubility (Choi et al., 2022; Costa et al., 2018). The presence of different types of NPs led to some variation in film solubility, with the lowest value of 2.77% obtained for Fe₂TiO₅-alginate films, and the highest of 7.49% for ZnO-alginate films.

Peaks characteristic for alginate films can be identified in the FTIR spectra, as shown in Fig. 3c (Dojcinovic, Vasiljevic, Kovac, Tadic, & Nikolic, 2021; Giz et al., 2020). The creation of new bonds or disappearance of bonds usually present in alginate film was not recorded after the addition of ZnO or Fe₂TiO₅ NPs. Only small differences in the range 800–400 cm⁻¹ mirrored the presence of Zn–O and/or Fe–O and Ti–O metal ion bands in the alginate film (Motelica et al., 2021; Rizzotto et al., 2022), although variation in peak intensity and minor shifts of some peaks characteristic for alginate films were noted. The intense pronounced band at ≈ 3255 cm⁻¹ is due to vibration of –OH groups. The shoulder at ≈ 2926 cm⁻¹ (alginate film) from –CH stretching vibrations (Lopusiewicz et al., 2022) revealed a minor shift due to the presence of ZnO and/or Fe₂TiO₅ NPs to around 2933 cm⁻¹. The characteristic vibrations for –CO in COO⁻ groups (asymmetric and symmetric) were noted at ≈ 1590 cm⁻¹ and 1413 cm⁻¹, respectively. The pronounced band at around 1024 cm⁻¹ (minor shift to 1022 cm⁻¹ for ZnO-alginate and ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅-alginate films) and shoulder at around 1078 cm⁻¹ (minor shift to 1080 cm⁻¹ for ZnO-alginate and ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅-alginate films) are ascribed to C–O–C bond stretching vibrations (Giz et al., 2020), while the range 800–1000 cm⁻¹ is the region of polysaccharide structures (Rizzotto et al., 2022).

Thermal stability of neat alginate, Fe₂TiO₅-alginate, ZnO-alginate and ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅-alginate composite films, followed using TG/DTA analysis, manifested two stage thermal decomposition (Fig. 3d). The first stage of weight loss of 15% occurred at around 100 °C and was due to elimination of adsorbed water. The second thermal degradation step took place at 200–360 °C and is caused by alginate thermal decomposition and glycerol evaporation (Shankar, Kasapis, & Rhim, 2018). Thermal stability of alginate films was to a certain degree enhanced by incorporation of ZnO and Fe₂TiO₅ NPs, as shown by the small difference in the TGA curves obtained. After the final thermal decomposition at 800 °C, the final residue for neat alginate film was 27.3%. This increased to 29.28% when the mixture of ZnO and Fe₂TiO₅ NPs was incorporated, confirming previous findings for composite alginate-NP films (Dash, Ali, Das, & Mohanta, 2019).

3.5. Preservation of fresh strawberry fruit

This study was done on freshly cut strawberries in open air conditions in order to verify the preservative effect of alginate, Fe₂TiO₅-alginate, ZnO-alginate and ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅ – alginate films on a food sample sensitive to oxidation (Fig. 4). Freshly cut strawberries

deteriorate visibly in open air. On the control sample this started on day 1 with some edge curling, while such edge spoilage was less noticeable when films were applied. More perceptible deterioration commenced on day 2, when the control sample revealed observable fruit tissue deterioration. The alginate film covered sample also displayed evident edge spoilage and some fruit tissue change on day 2. This was also observed for ZnO-alginate samples, while Fe₂TiO₅ – alginate and ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅ – alginate samples displayed only slight edge discoloration. On day 3 there was evident spoilage and fungal growth on the control sample, while those covered by films were less affected. The alginate and ZnO-alginate protected samples showed more observable spoilage than the Fe₂TiO₅-alginate and ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅-alginate film protected samples on day 3. On day 4 tissue was discoloured more in the strawberry sample covered with ZnO-alginate film when compared to the Fe₂TiO₅ – alginate sample. Overall strawberry protection was most improved by the ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅ – alginate film, indicating the beneficial influence of both types of NPs incorporated into the alginate matrix.

4. Conclusions

Active alginate films incorporating antioxidant Fe₂TiO₅ and antimicrobial ZnO nanoparticles were obtained using the solution casting method. Pure phase ZnO and Fe₂TiO₅ nanoparticles (with particle sizes of 10 and 50 nm, respectively) were obtained by green synthesis using citrus peel extract. The presence of ZnO and Fe₂TiO₅ nanoparticles in the film resulted in a synergistic effect, giving the lowest swelling degree, improved thermal stability, UV light protection, good transparency and opacity. When the protective activity of alginate packaging films containing ZnO NPs and Fe₂TiO₅ NPs separately or as a mixture was tested on freshly cut strawberries, protection was most enhanced by the ZnO/Fe₂TiO₅ – alginate film.

The results of this study provide a comprehensive view of various aspects of reinforcement of alginate films with ZnO and Fe₂TiO₅ NPs. Both nanoparticles may also be applicable for reinforcement of other biodegradable and environmentally friendly green polymers, such as

Fig. 4. Preservation study of freshly cut strawberry halves.

chitosan or zein. However, to achieve the ultimate goal of a highly efficient and safe food packaging material, the next challenging issue will consist of assessing and establishing the fate of metal oxide NPs obtained by green synthesis after release into the intestinal tract or the environment. Such further study is necessary prior to use in actual food systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jasmina Vidic: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Maria Vesna Nikolic:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Goran Miskovic:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Nenad B. Tadic:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Milena P. Dojcinovic:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Zorka Z. Vasiljevic:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jovana Vunduk:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Jasmina Vidic reports administrative support and travel were provided by European Commission.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.fpsl.2024.101280](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fpsl.2024.101280).

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